

NOVEL PULP FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The reinforcement potential of short pulp natural fibers in thermoplastic polymer composites was investigated using china reed fibers and cellulose diacetate (CDA), a compatible polymer matrix. The Young's modulus and tensile strength of pulp fibers were found to be equal to 60 GPa and 900 MPa, respectively, values which are twice as high compared to those of ground china reed particles. In addition, the aspect ratio of the pulp fibers was found to be 12 times higher than that of ground fiber bundles. The analysis of the mechanical properties of composites compression molded from CDA compounded with ground china reed, and from pulp fiber/CDA pre-forms, indicates that whereas ground china reed particles act as fillers increasing composite stiffness, a remarkable reinforcement effect was observed for the pulp fiber reinforced impregnated pre-forms. A combination of a stiffness increase by a factor 5.2 and a strength increase by a factor of 2.3 relative to the pure polymer was achieved, in contrast with typical pulp fiber reinforced thermoplastics, for which the stiffness increase is frequently obtained at the expense of loss in strength. These results indicate that pulp fibers are interesting low-weight and low-cost alternatives to short glass fibers for injection molding thermoplastic grades.

KEYWORDS: natural fibers, preforming methods, zero-span test, mechanical properties

INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastics reinforced with biomass materials offer numerous advantages over traditional polymer composites, including low density and high specific properties, low cost, safe fiber handling, high possible filling levels, low energy consumption, biodegradability and recyclability, a wide variety of fiber types, and generation of a rural/agricultural-based economy [1]. A large potential for energy savings and reduction of environmental impacts was demonstrated in a comparative life cycle assessment on the use of pulped lignocellulosic fibers vs. glass-fibers in transport pallets [2]. Long fibers from non-wood plants such as flax and hemp are used in natural fiber-mat reinforced thermoplastics, which have found widespread use within the automotive industry for non-critical applications such as lining elements, where stiffness is the only performance requirement [3]. Particles such as ground particles, flour, pulp, and old newsprint (ONP) are also frequently used as reinforcement agents. In the latter case the reinforcing phase is short-fiber or particle-like, which allows these composites to be processed by injection molding.

Pulp fibers, which are the focus of the present work, have an inherent advantage in higher aspect ratio and higher thermal stability than that of ground particles. Currently, a wide variety of pulp fibers are being used for reinforcement of thermoplastics [3], although their reinforcement potential is far from being fully exploited. The reason is that the fibers are extracted for use in papermaking where the objective is to maximize the bonded surface between fibers in order to ensure the mechanical integrity of the paper. In contrast, dispersed fibers are a prerequisite towards reinforcement efficiency in composites. Furthermore, currently used melt processing methods comprise several severe thermomechanical steps inducing premature degradation of the fibers.

Further development of pulp fibers reinforced thermoplastic composites requires systematic studies of i) fiber pulping methods, ii) composite preforming methods and iii) fiber and composite mechanical properties. The first two topics were detailed elsewhere [4; 5], and the aim of the present work is to investigate the effect of extraction and process methods on the mechanical properties of the fibers and of their composites with a thermoplastic matrix.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Miscanthus x giganteus, commonly named china reed, was chosen as the fiber source for its fast growth and thick-walled fibers. Two types of fiber were used: ground particles and pulped fibers, as shown in Figure 1. The ground particles (Genossenschaft Biomasse Technologie, Switzerland) were obtained by a double-pass grinding and sifting process with a 2x2 mm screen mounted on a shaking frame, giving coarse particles with residual parenchyma. Their weight average length and aspect ratio are respectively equal to 1.57 mm and 6.9. The pulp fibers were extracted using an alkali-methanol-anthraquinone (AMA) pulping procedure [5], giving individual, slender fibers. Their weight average length and aspect ratio are respectively equal to 1.09 mm and 81, that is, a factor 12 increase compared to the ground particles. The intrinsic density of the fibers is equal to $1.5306 \pm 0.0013 \text{ g/cm}^3$ as measured by helium pycnometry, i.e. excluding the hollowness of the fibers. Table I summarizes the fiber dimensions, determined from particle size analysis (STFI FiberMaster 2).

Figure 1. Ground particles (fiber bundles, left) and pulp fibers (right).

Table I. Number and weight average particle length (l), diameter (d), aspect ratio (r), shape factor (f), mechanical properties (Tensile modulus, E , and strength, σ_f [8]), and specific property/cost values.

Fibers	l_n [mm]	l_w [mm]	d_n [μm]	d_w [μm]	r_n	r_w	E [GPa]	$E/\rho \cdot \text{cost}$ [GPa·m ³ /\$]	σ_f [MPa]	$\sigma_f/\rho \cdot \text{cost}$ [MPa·m ³ /\$]
Ground	1.24	1.57	186	225	6.7	6.9	27.1 ± 2.5^1	26	422 ± 6.5^1	400
Pulped	0.552	1.086	13.45	13.70	40.3	80.7	59.5 ± 0.4^2	57	913 ± 79^2	850
									889 ³	
Glass	-	-	-	-	-	-	72	15	1'500	300

1. Extrapolation of tensile data at different gauge lengths to the number average fiber length.
2. Extrapolation of tensile data at different gauge lengths to the number average fiber length and assuming fiber bundles to be the only load carrying entity in the sample cross section.
3. Calculated from zero-span tensile tests on 2D randomly oriented paper.

Cellulose diacetate (CDA, Bioceta[®] 6V30S T29-12, Mazzucchelli1849 Spa, Italy), an amorphous thermoplastic polymer with a glass transition temperature equal to approximately 50°C and a density equal to 1.27 g/cm³, was selected as the polymer matrix for its inherent compatibility with the fibers. The CDA is plasticized with two non-phthalate plasticizers at proportions of 1:3 for a total plasticizer content of 30% by weight.

Manufacture of ground particle reinforced CDA composites

Ground china reed, dried for 12 hours under vacuum at 105°C was dry-blended with CDA pellets and subsequently compounded in a PRISM co-rotating twin screw extruder at 20 rpm with a nozzle pressure of approximately 15 bar and a residence time of approximately 1 min. The temperature profile of the extrusion step was 170°C, 200°C and 191°C for the feed-zone, compression-zone and the nozzle, respectively. Compounds with 18, 23, 46 and 54% by volume of ground China reed were extruded. At 54% by volume the extruded strand kept falling apart, indicating an upper level of particle content for extrusion with this material. The strands were pelletized and stored in a dessicator until final molding into 140x60 mm² plaques in a Fontijne hydraulic press. Mold pressure was kept at 10 bar for all samples containing up to 23% vol. of fibers. Pressures of 20 and 30 bar were used for the materials containing 46 and 54% vol., respectively. The thermal cycle consisted in heating at 20°C/min from ambient temperature to 200±3°C, which was held for 8 min followed by a cooling ramp of 20°C/min down to ambient temperature. Pressure was applied at the beginning of the isothermal step and was maintained during cooling. The final thickness of the ground China reed reinforced plaques was 2.2-2.4 mm, i.e. more than ten times the maximum particle thickness.

Manufacture of pulp fiber reinforced CDA composites

In a first step, the pulp fibers were spray dried into a loose wad, in order to reduce the density of fiber-fiber bonds, which was mixed with CDA dissolved into acetone puriss p.a. at 1:10 SL at room temperature, to fiber vol. fraction equal to 10% and 40%. The solvent was evaporated under ambient conditions of humidity and temperature until the resulting fiber network could be considered dry. It was verified that acetone did not soften the fibers, and that a good impregnation was achieved with the polymer covering the surface of the fibers. In a second step, impregnated pre-forms were dried at 80°C under vacuum for 12 hours and compression molded into 60 mm diameter discs using the same thermal cycle as for the ground china reed composites. The thickness of the molded discs was equal to 0.92±0.07 mm.

Characterization techniques

The tensile properties of fiber bundles were determined from testing china reed stems at three gauge lengths (15.5, 20 and 43.8 mm) to account for size dependent strength, using an UTS tensile tester at a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min. The data was corrected for effective load bearing cross section, assuming that parenchyma cells carry no tensile load.

The tensile strength of the pulp fibers was evaluated by means of zero-span tensile index measurements on a PULMAC Zero-span tester 3000. The zero span tester is an instrument in which a paper sample of known grammage (g/m²) is tested in tension with the clamps holding the sample adjusted to the shortest possible initial distance between them. Frequently the result is presented as zero-span tensile index (Nmg⁻¹), which corresponds to the zero span tensile strength divided by the grammage of the tested fiber sheet. Two factors contribute to the measured strength value: fiber orientation distribution and pulp fiber properties. The zero-span tests in this investigation were made on unbeaten fibers according to ISO 15361:2000 (E) using rewet fiber sheets. During measurements it was assumed that the tensile loading of paper entails the loading of the fibers, which permitted the determination of their strength. Not all fibers

were in direct contact with the clamps, however. Rupture of fiber-fiber bonds may thus also be a contributing factor to the measured value, although the test is designed to minimize this influence. Cowan recommended wetting of the fiber-sheet in order to minimize the contribution from fiber-fiber bond rupture [6]. More recent studies claim that fiber-fiber bonding has little effect on zero span tensile strength and that the argument for elimination of fiber bonds has no foundation [7].

The tensile behavior of the compression-molded composites was determined using MIII specimens (ASTM D 638M) for the ground material. Pulp reinforced composites were machined into dog-bone test specimens with a width of 3 mm. All composite samples were tested on an UTS tensile tester using extensometers at a nominal deformation rate of 0.09 s^{-1} . Ten samples were tested for each of the ground china reed reinforced composites and three samples were tested for each of the pulp fiber reinforced materials.

The microstructure of the composites was studied under a Philips XLF-30 scanning electron microscope in order to determine on the one hand, the level of lumen compression as a function of fiber volume fraction and processing pressure, and on the other hand to investigate the matrix-fiber interaction. All samples were sputter coated with gold and examined under an acceleration voltage of 2kV. The lumen compression was studied on samples polished during with silicon carbide paper of fineness in a sequence P#500, P#1000, P#2400 and P#4000, each one for a time of 2 minutes, whereas the matrix-fiber interaction was studied on tensile rupture surfaces.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tensile properties of ground particles and pulp fibers

The mechanical properties of the ground particles and pulp fibers of number average length were determined from extrapolation of the experimental data on stem coupons of various gauge length [8], and reported in Table I. The Young's modulus and tensile strength of the ground particles are found equal to $27.1 \pm 2.5 \text{ GPa}$ and $422 \pm 6.5 \text{ MPa}$, respectively. These values represent the average response of parenchyma cells and fiber bundles. However, there are likely to overestimate the real properties of ground particles, since grinding-induced cracks in the middle lamella of fiber bundles are not accounted for, which undoubtedly would have a detrimental effect on transverse fiber properties. Correcting for the surface fraction of parenchyma cells determined from image analysis of polished cross sections of the tensile samples gives values of Young's modulus and tensile strength of $59.5 \pm 0.4 \text{ GPa}$ and $913 \pm 79 \text{ MPa}$, respectively. These values are expected to be representative of the stiffness and strength of pulped fibers, and are in fact in the same order of magnitude as those of pineapple fibers [9].

Specific modulus- and specific strength-to-cost ratio, also reported in Table I, are typically three times higher for pulp fibers, compared to glass fibers. This important result indicates that pulp fibers are interesting low-weight and low-cost alternatives to short glass fibers for injection molding thermoplastic grades, providing the mechanical performance of the pulp fiber composite is equivalent to the glass fiber alternative.

Analysis of zero-span tensile tests

Unbeaten china reed pulp fibers exhibit excellent zero-span failure load, with values up to 187 Nm/g . For comparison, Håkanson reported a zero-span failure load of 100 Nm/g for beaten unbleached ethanol-alkali pulped reed canary grass, a similar species to *Miscanthus x giganteus* [10]. These values represent the strength of a randomly oriented 2D structure of fibers. The following analysis was developed to calculate the longitudinal tensile strength of individual pulp fibers (required for modeling of composite

tensile strength) from measured zero-span values, based on Van den Akker [11] and Boucai [12] analyses:

$$Z = \Psi N \Phi F \quad (1)$$

where Z is the paper zero-span failure load, N is the number of load carrying fibers, Φ is a factor accounting for fiber orientation, equal to $3/8$ for a randomly oriented 2D network [13] and F is the unknown average specific force at failure of fibers in the tested sheet. The factor Ψ is a probability function, which governs the fraction of fibers in a random aggregate that will cross both of two adjacent clamping lines, relative to the number that will cross either of the lines alone [12]:

$$\Psi = \frac{2}{\pi} \left[\left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{\partial}{l_n} \right) \right) - \frac{\partial}{9l_n} \sqrt{1 - \frac{\partial^2}{l_n^2} \left(7 + \frac{2\partial^2}{l_n^2} \right)} \right] \quad (2)$$

where ∂ is the residual span and l_n the number average fiber length. Whereas the above expression is useful to generate information on the force required to break a fiber it does not permit calculating the tensile stress in the fiber cross section at the moment of failure, unless the exact degree of hollowness of the fibers is known. Knowing the absolute density of the fibers in the tested sheets and their grammage, the tensile strength of the paper, σ_{paper} , is calculated as based on the load carrying section of fibers:

$$\sigma_{\text{paper}} = \frac{ZG}{G/\rho} = Z\rho \quad (3)$$

where G is the grammage of the tested sheets and ρ the intrinsic density of the fibers. Taking the random 2D fiber distribution into account, the longitudinal tensile strength of the fibers, σ_{fibers} , thus becomes:

$$\sigma_{\text{fibers}} = \frac{Z\rho}{\Psi\Phi} \quad (4)$$

Using the number average fiber length of the fibers, and assuming a residual span of 0.1 mm [14] Eq. 4 yields a longitudinal tensile fiber strength of 889 MPa for the pulp fibers, in very good agreement with the value determined in the above section, from tensile testing of the stem coupons.

These results indicate that the pulped china reed fibers are more adapted for the reinforcement of plastics than the ground china reed. The weight average aspect ratio is improved from 7 for ground fibers to 80 by pulping. Pulping yields single fibers of high straightness with strength and stiffness more than twice that of ground particles, which is likely to lead to a considerable increase of the reinforcing efficiency of the fibers. In addition, pulping increases the specific surface of the fibers by reducing size. If one assumes equal density of the ground and pulped china reed, at a particle volume fraction of 0.2 the ground particles will provide 4.6 cm² of interfacial surface per cm³ of composite, whereas the pulps will provide 59 cm² per cm³, that is, an order of magnitude increase. All these factors are likely to contribute to significantly better mechanical properties of the final composites [15], provided that the shape and the mechanical properties of the reinforcing phase are preserved during processing.

Composite tensile behavior and microstructural damage

The tensile behavior of the two composite types, with 40 vol% reinforcement, is shown in Fig. 2 and compared to that of the pure CDA matrix polymer. It is evident that the addition of ground china reed

Figure 2. Tensile behavior of 40 vol% pulp reinforced CDA composites, compared to that of the CDA matrix in the low strain range. Process optimization (impregnation) enables combined increase of strength and stiffness, by contrast with traditional composites reinforced with ground fibers.

particles confers stiffness to the composite, a result of the inherent stiffness of the ground particles, but reduces strength, which is characteristic of particulate reinforcements with low interaction with the matrix. Such lack of interaction can not be attributed to incompatibility of the matrix material with the fibers since both have very similar chemical structure. Rather, it reflects the presence of a weak stress transfer in the interfacial region between the CDA polymer and the lignocellulosic material. The reason for the poor interface is without doubt due to the residual parenchyma remaining on fiber bundles acting as a weak interface. Furthermore, the middle lamella in the fiber bundles constitutes yet another weak point in the structure that will contribute negatively to strength and elongation at break. Analysis of the rupture surface showed that specimen failure always involved considerable longitudinal shear (Fig. 3a). This is typical for wood-like structures containing several fiber bundles. One fiber bundle fails in tension and the crack propagates by longitudinal shear through the weak parenchyma cells until it reaches another fiber bundle, which then fails in tension.

In contrast, pulped china reed fibers increase to a considerable extent both strength and stiffness. At 40% vol. of pulp fibers the Young's modulus is equal to 8.7 ± 0.7 GPa and the tensile strength 79.4 ± 3.1 MPa. However, as for the ground China reed, the elongation to break is reduced significantly by the addition of pulp fibers. The improved mechanical properties of the pulp fiber reinforced composites are due to several factors. Mechanical properties are in general improved as the size of the reinforcing phase diminishes [15]. In addition the aspect ratio of the pulp fibers is more than ten times higher than that of the china reed particles, which permits better stress transfer between the matrix and the fibers. Fig. 3b depicts fiber tensile rupture surfaces and pullout lengths of the order of 20 μm . The fiber surfaces exhibit intimate contact with the resin, an indicative of good fiber-matrix adhesion.

In order to confirm the conservation of the reinforcement potential of the fibers as reflected by their mechanical properties, the stiffness and strength of the generated composites were modeled and compared to experimental values.

Figure 3a. Shear failure of ground particles on the fracture surface of a fiber reinforced CDA composite. Such failure mechanism is indicative of the poor reinforcement efficiency of the ground particles.

Figure 3b. Tensile failure of hollow pulp fibers on the fracture surface of a fiber reinforced CDA composite. Such failure mechanism is indicative of the high reinforcement efficiency of the pulp fibers.

Modeling of composites tensile behavior

The Young's modulus of the CDA composites, E_c , reinforced with either ground particles, or pulp fibers, was calculated following the classic approach developed by Halpin and Tsai, approximated as follows in case of in-plane random orientation of the fibers [16]:

$$E_c = \frac{3}{8} E_1 + \frac{5}{8} E_t \quad (5)$$

Where E_1 and E_t represent the longitudinal and transverse moduli of the composite with unidirectional reinforcement, respectively. Details of the modeling procedure are reported in ref. [4]. Fig. 4 compares experimental data to the Halpin-Tsai prediction using fiber stiffness values deduced from analysis of the tensile tests, as detailed in the preceding section. The good agreement with experimental data evident for pulped fibers confirms that the tensile performance of these fibers was preserved during processing, and that their reinforcement efficiency was fully exploited in the composite. The stiffness values for ground fibers are systematically overestimated. This implies that the grinding procedure induces damage to the fiber bundles in terms of bundle cracks, which severely reduce the transverse stiffness of the ground particles. The mechanical tests performed on stem sections do not take this type of damage into account.

The tensile strength of the composites, σ_c , was modeled as a simplification of the Kelly-Tyson analysis using the expression [17]:

$$\sigma_c = \sigma_m V_m + \varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_0 \sigma_f V_f \quad (6)$$

where σ_i represents tensile strength of phase i , as derived in the preceding section, with the subscripts m and f standing for matrix and fibers, respectively. The factor ε_0 represents the orientation of the fibers in the composite, taken to be equal to $1/3$. This value corresponds to in-plane random fiber orientation [18], which is the case for all studied composites, since the random orientation of the fibers in the pre-forms

Figure 4. Experimental (dots) and theoretical (lines) composite modulus vs. fiber volume fraction. See text for details.

was kept during the molding operation. The factor ε_1 represents the efficiency of load transfer between the fiber and the matrix, which remained the only fitting parameter in the expression. This parameter takes the value 0.012 ± 0.025 in the case of ground china reed and 0.61 ± 0.015 in the case of pulped fibers, showing considerably higher reinforcement efficiency in the case of the pulped fibers. The extremely low value of reinforcement efficiency obtained for the ground fibers further confirms the presence of weak points in the structure in terms of residual parenchyma located on the surface of the fiber bundles and on the presence of cracks in the middle lamella of these bundles, in addition to the low aspect ratio of the particles.

It is clear from a comparison of the ground and pulped China reed that the former particles act as a non-reinforcing filler, whereas the pulped fibers act as reinforcement in the composites increasing both strength and stiffness, regardless of whether the composite is processed at high or low pressure. At a fiber volume fraction of 0.4, the modulus and tensile strength of the pulp fiber composite are respectively 5.2 and 2.3 times higher than those of the plain polymer, and 2.6 and 4.6 times higher than those of the ground china reed equivalent. The values of elongation to break of the two composite types, on the other hand, remain essentially identical. Hanselka [19] found a tensile strength of 72 MPa and a Young's modulus of 5 GPa for CDA reinforced with 48%vol. woven flax linen tested in the warp direction. Compared to this value, the reinforcement achieved with the randomly oriented short pulp fibers is indeed remarkable.

This work highlights the key factors which control the mechanical performance of pulp fiber reinforcements previously neglected in literature, and demonstrates the remarkable reinforcement potential of such renewable material. Furthermore, the properties achieved by optimizing the extraction and processing steps indicate that pulp fiber reinforced thermoplastics composites are appropriate materials for load bearing applications.

CONCLUSIONS

The reinforcement potential of short pulp natural fibers in thermoplastic polymer composites was investigated using china reed fibers and cellulose diacetate, a compatible polymer matrix. Composites were compression molded from CDA compounded with up to 54%vol. ground china reed, and from pulp fiber/CDA pre-forms with up to 40%vol. fibers. The analysis of the mechanical performance of the ground particles and the pulp fibers, and their respective composites with CDA lead to the following conclusions:

The pulp fibers were found to possess excellent mechanical properties, with Young's modulus equal to approx. 60 GPa and tensile strength equal to 900 MPa. These values are twice as high compared to those of ground particles, and, combined with an aspect ratio 12 times higher than that of ground fiber bundles, indicate that pulp fibers are interesting low-weight and low-cost alternatives to short glass fibers for injection molding thermoplastic grades.

The ground china reed particles was found to act as fillers, stiffening the matrix material, but severely reducing ultimate properties, a result of poor interfacial stress transfer due to residual parenchyma on the fiber bundles and to longitudinal fiber bundle rupture due to grinding-induced cracks in the fiber bundles.

By contrast, a remarkable reinforcement effect was achieved with the pulp fiber reinforced impregnated pre-forms. Improvements by factors of 5.2 and 2.3 times compared to the plain polymer were observed for Young's modulus and tensile strength, respectively. This combination of strength and stiffness increase was found to be unique for this type of materials when comparing mechanical properties of the present composites with results from literature. Such properties are a prerequisite for the introduction of natural fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites into load bearing applications.

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